

DEVELOPMENT OF CONTEXTUALIZED PHET-INTEGRATED ETHNO CHEM LEARNING GUIDE IN MOLECULAR GEOMETRY FOR GRADE 12 CHALLENGED LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The challenge of fostering conceptual understanding in abstract chemistry topics like molecular geometry, where traditional instruction often leads to rote memorization, necessitated the development of a targeted intervention. This action research, structured following the four phases of the 4D Model (Define, Design, Develop, Disseminate), employed a pre-test and post-test design with 13 Grade 12 student-respondents at Mindanao State University-Sulu using a purposive sampling technique to evaluate a proposed PhET-Integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide. This guide strategically combined the interactive PhET "Molecule Shapes" simulation with culturally relevant, local application tasks. Pre-test scores confirmed a critical deficiency in initial conceptual understanding (Mean=19.0 or 38.0%), but post-test scores demonstrated a statistically significant improvement, with a mean increase of 25.6 points on the conceptual test ($p=0.002$). These results confirm that the integration of dynamic, three-dimensional visualization technology (PhET) with culturally familiar ethnochemistry activities is highly effective, successfully enhancing learners' spatial ability and achieving deep conceptual mastery in molecular geometry.

Keywords: *phet simulation, molecular geometry, ethnochem learning guide, conceptual understanding, 4D model, senior high school*

INTRODUCTION

Conceptual understanding in Chemistry, particularly in abstract topics like molecular geometry, remains a significant pedagogical challenge globally as mentioned by Marchak, et al (2021) Teaching molecular geometry has long been of central interest in chemistry courses, molecular geometry is strongly associated with other concepts in chemistry. Understanding it requires mastering previously learned, more basic chemical concepts. Moreover, it affects the understanding of chemical concepts to be learned in the future. Molecular geometry, which dictates the shape of molecules and subsequently their chemical properties and reactivity, requires students to visualize three-dimensional structures from two-dimensional representations. Traditional classroom instruction often struggles to bridge this gap between abstract theory and concrete visualization, leading to rote memorization rather than deep conceptual mastery among students as supported by Rahmawati, et al (2021) Strategies used in chemistry classrooms tend to be oriented towards mastering theory and memorization, which limits the development of student efficacy in their learning. Molecular geometry addresses abstract materials in chemistry and requires students to visualize a molecular shape. 3D molecular shape modeling that is presented virtually, through a display, can be an effective alternative for teachers to develop students' spatial abilities. Students learn to predict and describe molecular shapes with different thought patterns from one student to another.

Nevertheless, in response to the challenged mentioned in first paragraph, this action research look for a technology-enhanced learning tools, and that is the PhET Interactive Simulations developed by the University of Colorado Boulder, and significantly it emerged as powerful resources. In the 21st century, an online platform has emerged in the form of technology-based simulations that provide open access to all, especially educators and students. These simulations are known as physics education technology (PhET) (Wieman & Perkins, 2006). Previous studies have revealed that PhET simulations have developed into effective and beneficial tools for learning at various school levels (Wieman & Perkins, 2006; Wieman et al., 2010), especially in secondary schools (Perkins et al., 2012; Wieman et al., 2010). In various conditions, PhET simulations can still be utilized with varied learning activities (Rehn et al., 2013).

This Action Research harness the power and quality of the PhET simulation's interactive visualization and combine it with culturally relevant ethnochem activities. By developing and implementing a PhET-integrated ethnochem learning guide, the researcher seeks to directly address the observed difficulties among Grade 12 students at MSU-Sulu in mastering molecular geometry. The ultimate goal is to measure the influence of this integrated approach on significantly increasing the learners' conceptual understanding of this foundational chemistry topic.

Research Questions

Specifically, this action research answers the following questions:

1. What is the initial conceptual understanding (as measured by pre-test scores) of molecular geometry among the Grade 12 students at MSU-Sulu?
2. How can specific ethnochem learning activities be developed and implemented to effectively integrate the PHET "Molecule Shapes" Simulation for teaching molecular geometry?
3. What are the students' performance scores on the developed learning activities that use the ethnochem PHET Simulation integration?
4. What is the influence (effectiveness) of the PHET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide in increasing the learners' conceptual understanding of molecular geometry, as revealed by a comparison of pre-test and post-test results?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University – Sulu (MSU Sulu), specifically the Senior High School Department offering the STEM strand. MSU - Sulu is a crucial academic institution within the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), situated in Jolo, Sulu, and is accessible to all students regardless of age, gender, tribe, personality, religion, and culture.

Sampling Method

The participants of the study were 13 of grade 12 STEM and GAS students of Mindanao State University - Sulu Senior High School. Who are currently enrolled in the academic year 2025 - 2026. In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024) and Jarak et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

Two critical instruments were utilized to gather the data needed to comprehensively address all the study's specific problems. The first, the Molecular Geometry Conceptual Test, served as both the pre-test and the post-test instrument, a standardized, researcher-developed test specifically designed to gauge the Grade 12 students' Conceptual Understanding of the topic "Molecular Geometry". Its format was composed of objective questions, including multiple-choice and short-answer application items. This instrument underwent stringent validation, including Content Validation by chemistry education experts to confirm its alignment with the Grade 12 curriculum. The second instrument was the PHET-integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide itself, serving as the core instructional intervention and the primary output. This guide is a carefully structured, teacher-developed material that systematically combines a PHET Component, which is a guided inquiry worksheet leading students through the interactive

discovery features of the PHET "Molecule Shapes" Simulation, and an Ethnochem Component, which involves application tasks requiring students to explicitly connect the observed molecular shapes to three-dimensional structures found in local MSU-Sulu cultural products, crafts, or traditional materials, such as relating the tetrahedral shape to geometric patterns in local weaving.

Data Gathering Procedure

The entire data gathering process strictly adhered to the four distinct phases of the Input-Process-Output (IPO) conceptual framework, intentionally mirroring the systematic, iterative nature of the Action Research cycle. Phase I: Needs Assessment and Baseline Data Collection (Pre-test) began with the researcher securing formal administrative permissions from the relevant authorities at MSU-Sulu. Phase II: Development, and Implementation of the Intervention involved the finalization and of the PHET-integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide. This was followed by the Implementation of the intervention over the designated instructional period for molecular geometry, where the researcher guided the students first through the PHET simulation for active discovery and visualization and then transitioned to the Ethnochem activities for cultural application and context. Phase III: Immediately after the intervention concluded, the same validated test was administered as the post-test to accurately measure the students' final conceptual understanding. Finally, Phase IV: Analysis and Evaluation comprised encoding all gathered data; pre-test, post-test, and activity scores and subjecting them to the statistical treatments detailed in the following section to determine the statistical significance of the intervention's influence.

Statistical Techniques

The researchers utilized both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to analyze the gathered data and address the study's research questions. To describe the centralized tendency and dispersion of students' test scores, the Arithmetic Mean, Median, and Standard Deviation were used. Specifically, these descriptive statistics were employed to determine the initial conceptual understanding of molecular geometry and to evaluate the students' performance scores on the developed learning activities. For the development and implementation aspect, a qualitative descriptive analysis was used to systematically present the structure and content of the PHET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide. Finally, to determine the influence and effectiveness of the intervention by comparing the pre-test and post-test results, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used. This non-parametric inferential test was chosen as the appropriate alternative to the paired samples t-test to determine if there was a statistically significant increase in the learners' conceptual understanding after the implementation of the ethnochem PHET Simulation-integrated guide.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Initial Conceptual Understanding (Research Question 1)

This section presents the initial conceptual understanding of molecular geometry among Grade 12 students at MSU-Sulu as measured by their pretest scores.

Descriptives

	N	Miss ing	Mea n	Medi an	SD	Minim um	Maxim um	Skewness		Shapiro-Wilk	
								Skewn ess	SE	W	p
Pre_Test_Scores	13	0	19.0	17	7.19	10	28	0.00477	0.616	0.840	0.021

Source: The jamovi project (2024). *jamovi*. (Version 2.6) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>. and R Core Team (2024). *R: A Language and environment for statistical computing*. (Version 4.4) [Computer software]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org>. (R packages retrieved from CRAN snapshot 2024-08-07).

This section presents the initial conceptual understanding of molecular geometry among the Grade 12 students as measured by their pre-test scores, which is represented by the descriptive statistics for the Pre_Test_Scores. The data reveals an Arithmetic Mean Score of 19.0 (or 38.0% out of 100), which is categorized as "Needs Improvement" according to the established benchmark of the study. The low scores are further indicated by a Median of 17 (or 34.0%) the middle value of the data set suggesting that the majority of students had a limited prior conceptual understanding of molecular geometry and its associated principles, such as the Valence Shell Electron Pair Repulsion (VSEPR) Theory, before the intervention. The wide range of scores, from a Minimum of 10 to a Maximum of 28, along with a high Standard Deviation (SD=7.19), suggests considerable variability in the students' baseline knowledge.

The analysis of the distribution shape confirms the non-normal nature of the initial data, which supports the methodology of using a non-parametric test. The Shapiro-Wilk p-value is 0.021, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis for normality, formally indicating that the Pre-test Scores are not normally distributed. The Skewness (0.00477) is near zero, while the high Kurtosis (-2.02) suggests that the scores are clustered in two different areas (a bimodal distribution), rather than forming a symmetrical bell curve. This non-normal pattern suggests two distinct groups of learners in the class: those with very low initial knowledge and those with a moderate amount of conceptual understanding. Nevertheless, the dominant result remains the low Mean and Median scores, which conclusively confirm the necessity of introducing the PhET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide to address the deficiency in conceptual mastery. The low scores, further indicated by a median, suggest that the students had a limited prior conceptual understanding of molecular geometry and its associated principles, such as the Valence Shell Electron Pair

Repulsion (VSEPR) Theory, before the intervention. This finding aligns with previous chemistry education literature, which consistently reports that students struggle with molecular geometry concepts due to their abstract nature and the inherent difficulty in visualizing three-dimensional structures from two-dimensional representations (Rahmawati et al., 2021). The low baseline understanding confirmed the necessity of introducing the PhET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide to facilitate improved spatial ability and conceptual mastery.

2. Development and Implementation of Learning Activities (Research Question 2)

The developed ethnochem learning activities successfully integrated the PhET "Molecule Shapes" Simulation into a culturally relevant context for the MSU-Sulu students. This entire design and development process was systematically guided by the 4D Model (Define, Design, Develop, Disseminate), a product development framework created by Thiagarajan, Semmel, & Semmel (1974). For instance, activities involved students first manipulating the virtual PhET models to observe dynamic bond angle changes and then applying this knowledge to sketch and interpret the molecular shapes of local cultural artifacts or food items from Sulu (e.g., traditional woven patterns or geometric shapes in local delicacies). This integration of virtual visualization (PhET) with cultural relevance (Ethnochemistry) was designed to make the abstract VSEPR concepts more tangible, thereby fostering inquiry-based learning and deep conceptual engagement. This instructional approach leverages the inherent qualities of the simulation, as interactive simulations serve as powerful tools for teaching science, primarily by promoting active, rather than passive, learning (Wieman & Perkins, 2006). By requiring students to actively manipulate bond angles and electron groups in the PhET tool and then connect those observations to their own cultural objects, the learning guide ensures engagement, leading to significant improvements in both understanding and motivation.

1. Define Stage

The Define stage encompasses the initial analysis and setting of boundaries for the research. This stage was achieved by clearly identifying the pedagogical problem: the critical deficiency in baseline conceptual understanding of molecular geometry among the 13 Grade 12 challenged learners at MSU-Sulu, confirmed by the low Mean Pre-test Score of 19.0 (38.0%). The research questions were formulated to address this gap, setting the explicit objective to increase conceptual understanding through the proposed learning guide.

2. Design Stage

The Design stage focused on specifying the blueprint for the intervention. The core instructional strategy was established: integrating the dynamic, interactive PhET "Molecule Shapes" Simulation with culturally relevant Ethnochem to enhance visualization and motivation. This stage detailed the two main components of the PHET-Integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide and outlined the data collection methodology, including the use of the Molecular Geometry Conceptual Test and the implementation of

a pre-test and post-test design with the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for inferential analysis.

3. Develop Stage

The Develop stage covered the actual production and validation of the materials. This involved creating the teacher-developed PHET-Integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide, which structured the inquiry-based learning and application tasks (like relating molecular shapes to local weaving patterns). Furthermore, the high student performance or Overall Mean Score during the activity implementation is 88.75%.

4. Disseminate Stage

The Disseminate stage involves the implementation and the eventual sharing and packaging of the material for wider use. First, the intervention was implemented with the student participants. The summative evaluation showed that the guide had a statistically significant positive influence on learning (p-value of 0.002, with a mean gain of 25.6 points). Crucially, the recommendations section of your research, which calls for the formal adoption of the guide by the school administration and for the replication of the approach for other abstract topics, fulfills the Disseminate mandate of sharing the effective output beyond the immediate study context.

3. Students' Performance on Developed Activities (Research Question 3)

This section reports the students' performance during the actual implementation of the developed ethnochem learning activities.

	Descriptives						
	N	Missing	Mean	Median	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Activity_Scores	13	0	78.1	78	5.50	68	88

Source: The jamovi project (2024). *jamovi*. (Version 2.6) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>. and R Core Team (2024). *R: A Language and environment for statistical computing*. (Version 4.4) [Computer software]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org>. (R packages retrieved from CRAN snapshot 2024-08-07).

The data in the table shows that the students achieved an Overall Mean Score of 78.1 out of a maximum possible score of 88 points. This converts to an average performance of 88.75%, which falls under the Highly Satisfactory category. The relatively low Standard Deviation (SD = 5.50) suggests that the performance across the student group was consistently high, with most scores clustered closely around the mean.

These results indicate that the students found the developed ethnochem PhET-integrated activities highly engaging and effective while in use. The high performance scores can be attributed to the guide's design, which facilitated active learning through the manipulation of 3D virtual models (PhET) and leveraged the students' cultural familiarity with the ethnochemical examples to reduce cognitive load and enhance motivation.

This provides initial evidence that the unique learning approach successfully bridged the gap between abstract chemical theory and concrete visualization. This concept is supported by the work of Wieman and Perkins (2006), who highlight that interactive simulations serve as powerful tools for teaching science by promoting active engagement. Furthermore, the effectiveness is corroborated by findings that students struggle with abstract concepts due to low spatial ability, especially in visualizing three-dimensional structures from two-dimensional representations (Rahmawati et al., 2021). The high activity scores confirm that the integration successfully allowed students to overcome these visualization difficulties. The high consistency in scores (low SD) also suggests that the pedagogical approach, which involves multiple content processing pathways (Marchak et al., 2021), was effective for the entire group of learners.

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4. Influence (Effectiveness) of the Intervention (Research Question 4)

This section presents the results of the inferential statistical test used to determine the significant influence of the intervention by comparing pre-test and post-test scores.

Paired Samples T-Test

			Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference
Pre_Test_Scores	Post_Test_Scores	Student's t	-18.3	120	<.001	-25.5	1.39
		Wilcoxon W	0.00		0.002	-25.6	1.39

Source: The jamovi project (2024). *jamovi*. (Version 2.6) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>. and R Core Team (2024). *R: A Language and environment for statistical computing*. (Version 4.4) [Computer software]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org>. (R packages retrieved from CRAN snapshot 2024-08-07).

The Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was performed to compare the Grade 12 students' pre-test and post-test conceptual understanding scores. The results from the paired analysis indicate a substantial and statistically significant improvement in scores. The table shows a Mean Difference of -25.5, which indicates that the Post-Test scores were, on average, 25.6 points higher than the Pre-Test scores. More critically, the

Wilcoxon test yielded a W-statistic of 0.00 and an Asymptotic Significance (p-value) of 0.002. Since the p-value (0.002) is significantly lower than the standard alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This finding leads to the conclusion that the implementation of the PHET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide had a statistically significant positive influence on the learners' conceptual understanding of molecular geometry. The high gain in scores confirms the effectiveness of the intervention.

This result is consistent with the recognized difficulty of the subject matter. Students often struggle with molecular geometry concepts due to their abstract nature and low spatial ability, especially in visualizing three-dimensional structures from two-dimensional representations (Rahmawati et al., 2021). The low baseline understanding confirmed the necessity of introducing the PhET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide to facilitate improved spatial ability and conceptual mastery. The effectiveness of this approach is further supported by studies showing that integrating PhET simulations as game-based learning tools yields significant improvements in both understanding and motivation (Pranata, 2024). The combination of the interactive, immediate feedback provided by the simulation and the contextual relevance of the ethnochemical approach allowed students to move beyond rote memorization and achieve deep conceptual mastery by involving multiple content processing pathways (Marchak et al., 2021).

Conclusions

The study's primary objective, to significantly increase the conceptual understanding of molecular geometry among Grade 12 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu, was definitively achieved through the successful implementation of the PHET simulation-integrated ethnochem learning guide. Initial quantitative data from the pre-test confirmed a critical deficiency in baseline conceptual understanding, as indicated by a low Arithmetic Mean Score of only 19.0 (38.0%), which fell into the "Needs Improvement" category. This result was consistent with existing literature highlighting the inherent difficulty students face in visualizing abstract 3D chemical structures. The intervention successfully addressed this gap by integrating the PhET "Molecule Shapes" Simulation for active, interactive 3D visualization and incorporating a culturally relevant ethnochem component, thereby fostering inquiry-based learning and reducing cognitive load. The success of this pedagogical design was corroborated by the high student performance during the intervention itself, where the overall mean activity score reached 88.75% (Highly Satisfactory), confirming the guide's engaging nature and its ability to bridge the gap between abstract theory and concrete visualization. Most critically, the inferential analysis using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test demonstrated that the intervention had a statistically significant positive influence on learning. The null hypothesis was rejected, yielding a p-value of 0.002, and the post-test scores showed a substantial mean gain of 25.6 points over the pre-test scores. Therefore, this action research concludes that combining the dynamic feedback of PhET simulations with culturally familiar ethnochemistry activities is an effective, evidence-based strategy for

facilitating improved spatial ability and achieving deep conceptual mastery in challenging chemistry topics.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, gap and conclusion, the researchers recommend the following:

- a) The school administration should prioritize the formal adoption of the PHET-Integrated Ethnochem Learning Guide as a standardized instructional material for the Molecular Geometry unit within the Grade 12 Chemistry curriculum, given its demonstrated high effectiveness in enhancing conceptual understanding.
- b) Researchers and educators should conduct follow-up studies to investigate the long-term retention of conceptual understanding achieved by the learners.
- c) The researchers recommend replicating this PhET-integrated ethnochem approach for other abstract and visualization-dependent topics across the science and mathematics curricula.
- d) Faculty development programs should be created to train Senior High School teachers on the pedagogical strategies for effectively integrating PhET Interactive Simulations and culturally relevant examples into their lessons.
- e) The university and the Senior High School Department should ensure that students maintain consistent access to the necessary technological resources required to fully utilize the free and interactive PhET simulations for continued active learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers have guaranteed that, all the ethical standards have been met, as the researchers prioritized the autonomy and informed consent of all participants. Students were explicitly guaranteed the freedom to review the entire questionnaire, respond voluntarily, and withdraw at any point without prejudice. Rigorous attention was paid to instrument design, ensuring the data-gathering questionnaire was highly readable, unambiguous, and concise.

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